

CHARACTER EDUCATION: COMPREHENSIVE, INTENTIONAL, AND PROACTIVE APPROACH IN DEVELOPING LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

The present study was focused on the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education and Learners' Development. The researcher assessed the profiles of the respondents, the extent of implementation of character education in terms of both academic curriculum and extracurricular programs, and the effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education for learners' development. The respondents in the study were public school teachers from selected districts in Quezon Province. The study employed a survey method for data collection. The researcher concluded that the demographic profile of the teachers, including their proficiency levels and educational backgrounds, had a significant impact on the implementation and effectiveness of character education. The implementation of character education was positively correlated with its effectiveness in promoting various aspects of learners' development, such as behavioral change, social-emotional skills, ethical decision-making, and peer-teacher relationships. The researcher recommended that schools integrate character education into all aspects of the curriculum and extracurricular activities, ensuring that programs are well-structured and regularly assessed for effectiveness. Further research is recommended to investigate additional variables and gain a deeper understanding of the effects of character education.

Keywords: *character education, teachers, implementation, effectiveness*

INTRODUCTION

Children's character education is a primary objective of socialization and education. Most parents want their children to grow up to be specific types of people with admirable and desirable qualities, and whose personalities possess a strong sense of ethics (Cervantes et al., 2022). The formation of moral character is regarded as the conventional objective of formal education, and it is at the forefront of educational efforts (Huitt & Tolbert, 2024; Nugraha et al., 2023). Character education is widely acknowledged as the foundation for developing responsible citizens and well-rounded individuals (Asri & Deviv, 2023).

The need to maximize character education becomes increasingly apparent, particularly at the elementary level of basic education. Since elementary learners are more susceptible to influences, a more thorough, deliberate, and proactive approach to character education is necessary throughout educational environments (Febriantina et al., 2021). Meeting the diverse needs of elementary students requires a comprehensive approach that is thoughtfully planned and executed with foresight. The goal is to create a dynamic environment that actively involves students in their path of character development, rather than just imparting qualities (Enizah et al., 2024).

Within the Philippine educational framework of the MATATAG curriculum, particularly in the Schools Division of Quezon Province, character education with values integration is highlighted (DepEd Schools Division of Quezon, 2024). As elementary learners navigate their formative years, the Schools Division provides an educational environment that not only imparts academic knowledge but also molds their character, laying the foundation for lifelong values and ethical decision-making.

In the midst of all this, the primary focus is on implementing a Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach to support elementary students' overall development. Teachers and administrators in the Schools Division of Quezon Province can change the educational landscape by taking the initiative. By doing so, they can provide elementary students with an enriching environment that goes beyond academics, nurtures their character, and prepares them for the challenges of a constantly changing society. A deliberate shift toward a more comprehensive and intentional character education paradigm is necessary (Sahertian & Effendi, 2022). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine, within the framework of the Quezon Province Schools Division, the effectiveness of character education through a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach.

Research Questions

This study aims to explore the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach to Character Education and Learners' Development in the Public Elementary Schools Division of Quezon Province.

Specifically, this research answered the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1. proficiency level;
- 1.2. educational background; and
- 1.3. Number of classes handled?
2. What is the extent of implementation of the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education in the school as perceived by teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. academic curriculum; and
 - 2.2. extracurricular program?
3. What is the level of effectiveness of the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach Character Education to learners' development as perceived by teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. behavioral change;
 - 3.2. social-emotional skills;
 - 3.3. ethical decision-making; and
 - 3.4. peer and teacher relationships?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the extent of implementation of the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the level of effectiveness of optimized character education to learners' development?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of implementation of optimized Character Education with a Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach and its level of effectiveness to learners' development as perceived by teachers?

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative research was employed to determine the effectiveness of a Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach to Character Education and learners' development in the Public Elementary Schools of Quezon Province. With the quantitative method, this approach facilitates a comprehensive exploration of the research questions.

Quantitatively, surveys and structured observations enable the collection of numerical data on the demographic profiles of teachers, as well as perceived data on the implementation and effectiveness of the character education approach.

The study was conducted because it would be beneficial to the Schools Division of Quezon Province to assess the effectiveness of implementing optimized Character Education with a Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach, and to employ strategies and approaches to integrate character development in elementary learners.

The study employed purposive sampling. Respondents were chosen from selected public elementary schools in the Schools Division of Quezon Province based on their knowledge of the information required by the researcher. According to Creswell & Creswell (2018),

purposive sampling involves deliberately choosing participants who can provide in-depth insights into a particular theme, concept, or phenomenon. This method means that not all elements of the population have an equal chance of being selected for the sample.

RESULTS

Table 1

Frequency and Distribution of Respondents in terms of Proficiency Level

Proficiency Level	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Teacher I	79	34.3	1
Teacher II	44	19.1	2
Teacher III	42	18.3	3
Master Teacher I	34	7.8	4
Master Teacher II	31	7.0	5
Total	230	100.0	

Table 2

Frequency and Distribution of Respondents in terms of Educational Background

Educational Background	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Bachelor's Degree	95	41.3	1
Master's Degree (CAR)	21	9.1	4
Master's Degree	54	23.5	2
Doctoral Degree (CAR)	12	5.2	5
Doctoral Degree	48	20.9	3
Total	230	100.0	

Table 3

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Number of Classes Handled

Number of Classes	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1-4	41	17.8	3
4-6	145	63.0	1
More than 6	44	19.1	2
Total	230	100.0	

Table 4

The Respondent's Extent to the Implementation of a Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education for Academic Curriculum

Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Character traits such as respect, responsibility, honesty, kindness, and determination are integrated into lessons and materials for all subjects.	3.59	0.764	Fully Implemented
The curriculum includes activities and discussions that encourage students to analyze moral dilemmas, consider different perspectives, and make informed ethical decisions.	3.63	0.679	Fully Implemented
Stories and texts are chosen to illustrate moral and ethical concepts and provoke discussions about character development.	3.62	0.707	Fully Implemented
Character education is systematically incorporated into the curriculum at all grade levels, with developmentally appropriate lessons and activities.	3.44	0.822	Mostly Implemented
There are formal and informal assessments or tests in place to measure students' growth in character traits and ethical reasoning skills.	3.31	0.900	Mostly Implemented

Overall Extent	3.52	0.350	Fully Implemented
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Legend: 3.51-4.00 – Fully Implemented, 2.51-3.50 – Mostly Implemented, 1.51-2.50 – In Progress, 1.00-1.50 – Not Implemented

Table 5

Respondent's Extent to the Implementation of a Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education for Extracurricular Programs

Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
A wide range of extracurricular activities, including clubs, sports teams, community service projects, and leadership programs, are offered to students.	3.53	0.813	Fully Implemented
Extracurricular programs are designed to align with the school's character education goals and reinforce positive character traits.	3.36	0.898	Mostly Implemented
Students have opportunities to take on leadership roles within extracurricular activities, focusing on skills such as communication, teamwork, and responsibility.	3.28	0.907	Mostly Implemented
Extracurricular activities provide opportunities for students to develop social and emotional skills, such as empathy, cooperation, and resilience.	3.57	0.771	Fully Implemented
Extracurricular programs are inclusive and accessible to all students, regardless of their background or abilities.	3.63	0.685	Fully Implemented
Overall Extent	3.47	0.390	Mostly Implemented

Legend: 3.51-4.00 – Fully Implemented, 2.51-3.50 – Mostly Implemented, 1.51-2.50 – In Progress, 1.00-1.50 – Not Implemented

Table 6

Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to learners' development in terms of Behavioral Change

Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
There are positive changes in student behavior.	3.61	0.726	Very Effective
Students demonstrate improved self-discipline and self-control.	3.43	0.827	Effective
Emphasis on ethical behavior encourages students to be honest and uphold integrity in both their academic and personal lives.	3.30	0.893	Effective
Students actively apply character traits such as respect, responsibility, and empathy in their interactions with others.	3.54	0.796	Very Effective
There is increased cooperation and collaboration among students in group activities and projects.	3.37	0.900	Very Effective
Overall Level of Effectiveness	3.45	0.470	Effective

Legend: 3.51-4.00 – Very Effective, 2.51-3.50 – Effective, 1.51-2.50 – Moderately Effective, 1.00-1.50 – Not Effective

Table 7

Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to Learners' Development in terms of Social-Emotional Skills

Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Students demonstrate improved emotional awareness and regulation skills.	3.53	0.823	Very Effective
Students feel more confident in managing emotions and coping with stress.	3.46	0.918	Effective
Students show empathy and compassion towards their peers.	3.36	0.904	Effective

Students develop stronger interpersonal skills, such as active listening and effective communication.	3.28	0.935	Effective
There is greater resilience and perseverance among students when facing academic or personal challenges.	3.46	0.918	Effective
Overall Level of Effectiveness	3.42	0.503	Effective

Legend: 3.51-4.00 – Very Effective, 2.51-3.50 – Effective, 1.51-2.50 – Moderately Effective, 1.00-1.50 – Not Effective

Table 8

Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to Learners' Development in terms of Ethical Decision-Making

Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Students feel more equipped to make ethical decisions and act with integrity in various situations.	3.30	0.906	Very Effective
Students demonstrate a deeper understanding of ethical principles and apply them in real-life scenarios.	3.53	0.802	Very Effective
Character Education activities encourage critical thinking and reflection on moral dilemmas, leading to more thoughtful decision-making.	3.36	0.894	Effective
Students take responsibility for their actions and consider the consequences of their choices.	3.27	0.910	Effective
There is a growing awareness of ethical issues and a greater willingness among students to stand up for what is right.	3.55	0.801	Very Effective
Overall Level of Effectiveness	3.40	0.461	Effective

Legend: 3.51-4.00 – Very Effective, 2.51-3.50 – Effective, 1.51-2.50 – Moderately Effective, 1.00-1.50 – Not Effective

Table 9

Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to Learners' Development in terms of Peer and Teacher Relationship

Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Students have developed stronger bonds with classmates through collaborative Character Education activities and discussions.	3.27	0.919	Very Effective
Students demonstrate respect and appreciation for individual differences in the classroom.	3.51	0.829	Very Effective
There is improved communication and understanding between students and teachers.	3.57	0.760	Very Effective
Students feel supported by teachers in personal and academic growth.	3.62	0.694	Very Effective
There is a positive and supportive classroom environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves and seeking help from teachers and classmates.	3.58	0.759	Very Effective
Overall Level of Effectiveness	3.51	0.397	Very Effective

Legend: 3.51-4.00 – Very Effective, 2.51-3.50 – Effective, 1.51-2.50 – Moderately Effective, 1.00-1.50 – Not Effective

Table 10

Significant Relationship Between the Demographic Profile of the Respondents and the Extent of Implementation of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education in terms of Academic Curriculum

Extent of Demographic Profile	Chi-square Value	df	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Proficiency Level	115.24	54	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Academic Curriculum	Educational Background	106.66	36	.000	Reject H _o	Significant
	Number of Classes Handled	17.21	18	.509	Failed to reject H _o	Not Significant

Legend: Significant if p<0.05

Table 11

Significant Relationship Between the Demographic Profile of the Respondents and the Extent of Implementation of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education in terms of Extracurricular Program

Extent of Implementation	Demographic Profile	Chi-square Value	df	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
	Proficiency Level	91.69	54	.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Extra-curricular Program	Educational Background	61.53	36	.005	Reject H _o	Significant
	Number of Classes Handled	22.12	18	.227	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant

Legend: Significant if p<0.05

Table 12

Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Respondents and Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to Learners' Development in terms of Behavioral Change

Level of Effectiveness	Demographic Profile	Chi-square Value	df	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
	Proficiency Level	134.26	60	.000	Reject H _o	Significant
Behavioral Change	Educational Background	80.36	40	.000	Reject H _o	Significant
	Number of Classes Handled	25.54	20	.182	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant

Legend: Significant if $p < 0.05$

Table 13

Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Respondents and Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to Learners' Development in terms of Social-Emotional Skills

Level of Effectiveness	Demographic Profile	Chi-square Value	df	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Social-Emotional Skills	Proficiency Level	112.28	66	.000	Reject H _o	Significant
	Educational Background	45.66	44	.403	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant
	Number of Classes Handled	34.32	21	.046	Reject H _o	Significant

Legend: Significant if $p < 0.05$

Table 14

Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Respondents and Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to Learners' Development in terms of Ethical Decision-Making

Level of Effectiveness	Demographic Profile	Chi-square Value	df	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
	Proficiency Level	86.08	60	.015	Reject H ₀	Significant
Ethical Decision-Making	Educational Background	52.80	40	.085	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
	Number of Classes Handled	25.99	20	.166	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant

Legend: Significant if p<0.05

Table 15

Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Respondents and Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to learners' development in terms of Peer and Teacher Relationship

Level of Effectiveness	Demographic Profile	Chi-square Value	df	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Peer and Teacher Relationship	Proficiency Level	94.20	60	.003	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Educational Background	72.80	40	.001	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Number of Classes Handled	51.13	20	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Legend: Significant if p<0.05

Table 16

Significant Relationship between the Extent of Implementation of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education and Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to Learners' Development

Extent of Implementation	Level of Effectiveness	Pearson r	Degree of Correlation	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Academic Curriculum	Behavior Change	0.78	Strong	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Social-Emotional Skills	0.71	Strong	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Ethical Decision Making	0.72	Strong	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Peer Teacher Relationship	0.68	Strong	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Legend: Significant if $p < 0.05$; 0.60-0.79 Strong correlation, 0.40-0.59 Moderate correlation, 0.20-0.39 Weak Correlation, 0.00-0.19 Very Weak / No correlation (Evans, 1996)

Table 17

Significant Relationship Between the Extent of Implementation of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education and the Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to Learners' Development

Extent of Implementation	Level of Effectiveness	Pearson r	Degree of Correlation	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Extracurricular Program	Behavior Change	0.83	Strong	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Social-Emotional Skills	0.69	Strong	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Ethical Decision Making	0.86	Strong	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Peer Teacher Relations hip	0.73	Strong	.000	Reject H _o	Significant
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Legend: Significant if $p < 0.05$; 0.60-0.79 Strong correlation, 0.40-0.59 Moderate correlation, 0.20-0.39 Weak Correlation, 0.00-0.19 Very Weak / No correlation (Evans, 1996)

DISCUSSION

Demographic profile of the respondents

The first specific problem addressed the demographic profile of the respondents, including their proficiency level, educational background, and attainment, as well as the number of classes they handle.

Table 1 shows the data on the proficiency level of the teacher respondents. 65 or 28.3% of teachers are categorized as Highly Proficient, while 165 or 71.7% of teachers are classified as Proficient. The total number of teacher respondents is 230. This indicates that, according to the Career Progression framework of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, the majority of teachers fall under the Proficient category, holding positions such as Teacher I to III (TI-TIII). Meanwhile, the Highly Proficient teachers hold positions such as Master Teachers I to IV (MTI-MTIV).

This aligns with Lee (2019), who explored the varying proficiency levels among teachers, ranging from Teacher I to Master Teacher IV. Teachers at different proficiency levels approached instructional strategies, classroom management, and student engagement, whereas at higher proficiency levels tended to demonstrate greater pedagogical expertise, leading to more positive learning experiences for students.

As depicted in the data on the educational background and attainment of the teacher respondents in Table 2, it is evident that 95 teachers, or 41.3%, hold a Bachelor's Degree. Additionally, 21 or 9.1% of teachers have a Master's Degree with Completed Academic Requirements (CAR), while 54 or 23.5% of teachers have attained a Master's Degree. Moreover, 12 or 5.2% of teachers possess a Doctoral Degree with Completed Academic Requirements (CAR), and 48 or 20.9% of teachers have earned a Doctoral Degree. The total number of teacher respondents is 230, representing all educational levels.

This agrees with Vural and Basaran (2021), who stated that when discussing educational background, teachers pursuing postgraduate studies have shared a variety of motivations. These include personal and professional development within the field of education, a desire to embark on an academic career, the aspiration to gain in-depth knowledge, and the aim to enhance the quality of their teaching practices by deepening their professional expertise. This diversity in educational qualifications reflects a broad range of expertise and experiences among the respondents. Furthermore, these figures

illustrate a commitment to continuous professional development across various academic stages.

Table 3 presents the demographic profile of the teacher respondents in terms of the number of classes they handle. It reveals that 41, or 17.8%, of teachers manage 1-4 classes. Meanwhile, 145 teachers, or 63%, handle 4-6 classes, and 44 teachers, or 19%, are responsible for more than six classes. The total number of teacher respondents is 230, indicating that the majority of teachers handle between 4-6 classes.

This aligns with the average number of classes handled in the Philippines, as approved by the Department of Education Order No. 54, series of 2008, which states that teachers who have 1 to 6 classes a day experience more meaningful learning (Cervantes et al., 2022).

Extent of Implementation of the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education

As shown in the findings in Table 4, with regards to the respondents' extent to the implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education for the academic curriculum, the indicator "Curriculum includes activities and discussions that encourage students to analyze moral dilemmas, consider different perspectives, and make ethical decisions" had obtained the highest mean of 3.63 and verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented.

In contrast, the indicator "There are formal and informal assessments or tests in place to measure students' growth in character traits and ethical reasoning skills," obtained the lowest mean of 3.31 and was verbally interpreted as Mostly Implemented.

The overall weighted mean for the extent of implementation was 3.52, indicating a level of implementation classified as 'Fully Implemented'. This suggests that, in terms of implementing a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education, there is a significant emphasis on engaging students in moral and ethical discussions and activities; however, there is less emphasis on formal and informal assessments to measure growth in these areas.

This aligns with Asri & Deviv (2023), who stated that implementing character education enables pupils to act and behave in accordance with the ideals that have become an integral part of their personalities. Character education is a continuous effort to cultivate good habits in learners. Not only should character education be provided in the context of schools, but it should also be reinforced at home and in the community's social settings.

Table number 5 with regards to the respondents' extent to the implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education for the extracurricular program, the indicator "Extracurricular programs are inclusive and

accessible to all students, regardless of their background or abilities” had the highest mean of 3.63 and was verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented.

In contrast, the indicator “Students have opportunities to take on leadership roles within extracurricular activities focusing on skills such as communication, teamwork, and responsibility” had the lowest mean of 3.28, with verbal interpretation of interpreted as or abilities” had the highest mean of 3.63, and with verbal interpretation of Mostly Implemented. Furthermore, the overall mean for the extent of implementation was 3.47, indicating a verbal interpretation of 'Mostly Implemented'. This suggests that implementing a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education through extracurricular programs is primarily achieved by ensuring inclusivity and accessibility for all students. At the same time, there is less emphasis on providing leadership opportunities that focus on communication, teamwork, and responsibility skills.

This finding aligns with Rahayu and Dong's (2023) research, which revealed that extracurricular activities are crucial for character development. The research demonstrates a proactive approach by highlighting deliberate planning for character development outside the classroom and recognizing the value of extracurricular activities, such as clubs and sports teams.

Effectiveness of a Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Character Education Approach to learners' development

Specific problem number 3 focuses on the effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education to learners' development in terms of Behavioral Change, Social-Emotional Skills, Ethical Decision Making, and Peer and Teacher Relationships.

Furthermore, as shown in the findings in Table 6, with regards to the level of effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education to learners' development in terms of behavioral change, the indicator “There are positive changes in student behavior” had the highest mean of 3.61 and with verbal interpretation of Very Effective. However, the indicator “Emphasis on ethical behavior encourages students to be honest and uphold integrity in both their academic and personal life” had the lowest mean of 3.30, with verbal interpretation as Effective. The overall mean for the level of effectiveness was 3.45, with a verbal interpretation of 'Effective'. This suggests that implementing a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education is most effective in promoting positive changes in student behavior and the active application of character traits, such as respect, responsibility, and empathy. At the same time, there is slightly less effectiveness in encouraging students to uphold integrity in their academic and personal lives.

This supports Huitt and Tolbert (2024), who stated that given the increasing visibility of trauma, crisis, and clinical challenges among children today, it is crucial that school professionals are equipped with the tools to establish a more consistent culture of care within their schools. Comprehensive and compassionate evidence-based practices in character education should be designed to sustainably transform young learners'

behavior and shift the perspectives of the adults who work with them. The ultimate goal is to foster an environment where students feel supported and understood, and where their behavioral and emotional needs are met through consistent, well-informed strategies.

In addition, as shown in the findings in Table 7, with regards to the level of effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education to learners' development in terms of social-emotional skills, the indicator "Students demonstrate improved emotional awareness and regulation skills" had the highest mean of 3.53 with verbal interpretation as Very Effective. On the other hand, the indicator "Students develop stronger interpersonal skills, such as active listening and effective communication" had the lowest mean of 3.28, with a verbal interpretation of "Effective." The overall mean for the level of effectiveness was 3.42 and interpreted as Effective. This indicates that the implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education is most effective in enhancing students' emotional awareness and regulation skills, while there is slightly less effectiveness in developing students' interpersonal skills, such as active listening and effective communication.

This aligns with Martinez & Partin's (2024) study, which found a favourable relationship between deliberate character education initiatives and the development of critical competencies, emphasizing the focused growth of abilities beyond academic knowledge. Specifically, students have shown notable advancements in emotional regulation, confidence in managing stress, empathy towards others, interpersonal skills, and resilience in overcoming challenges.

As shown in the findings in Table 8, with regards to the level of effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education to learners' development in terms of ethical decision-making, the indicator "There is a greater awareness of ethical issues and a willingness to stand up for what is right among students" had the highest mean of 3.55 and interpreted as Very Effective. On the other hand, the indicator "Students take responsibility for their actions and consider the consequences of their choices" had the lowest mean of 3.27 and was interpreted as Effective. The overall mean for the level of effectiveness was 3.40, with a verbal interpretation of 'Effective'. This suggests that implementing a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education is most effective in increasing students' awareness of ethical issues and their willingness to stand up for what is right. At the same time, there is a slight decrease in effectiveness in ensuring that students take responsibility for their actions and consider the consequences of their choices.

This agrees with Enizah and Marleni's (2024) research, which examined character education and ethical decision-making. It emphasizes the holistic approach and the necessity of character education, addressing moral reasoning and ethical issues within the educational framework. Additionally, students demonstrate responsibility for their

actions and a heightened awareness of ethical issues, creating a culture of ethical behavior and moral courage.

Finally, as shown in the findings in Table 9, with regards to the level of effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education to learners' development in terms of peer and teacher relationships, the indicator "Students feel supported by teachers in personal and academic growth" had the highest mean of 3.62 interpreted as Very Effective. On the other hand, the indicator "Students have developed stronger bonds with classmates through collaborative Character Education activities and discussions" had the lowest mean of 3.27, interpreted as Effective. The overall mean for the level of effectiveness was 3.51, indicating a level of effectiveness that is interpreted as "Very Effective." This suggests that implementing a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education is most effective in fostering a supportive classroom environment and enhancing communication and understanding between students and teachers. At the same time, there is a slight decrease in the effectiveness of developing stronger bonds among classmates through collaborative activities and discussions.

Evlat and Avcioğlu (2022) also examined the relationship between character education and peer-teacher relationships, specifically with children who have special needs. They revealed that activities can positively impact the quality of relationships between learners and instructors, as well as among learners themselves, which is consistent with the holistic nature of character education. Students exhibit enhanced bonds with peers, demonstrate respect for diversity, experience improved communication with teachers, feel supported in their personal and academic growth, and thrive in a positive classroom environment.

Significant Relationship Between the Demographic Profile of the Respondents and the Extent of Implementation of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education

Table 10 presents the Significant Relationship Between the demographic profile of the respondents and the extent of implementation of the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education in terms of the Academic Curriculum. The results showed that educational background (p -value = 0.000) and the proficiency level of teachers (p -value = 0.001) significantly impact the extent of implementation of the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education within the Academic Curriculum. The number of classes handled has no significant relationship (p -value = 0.509) to the extent of implementation.

Thus, the null hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the extent of implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education in terms of academic curriculum is rejected. This aligns with Sahertian and Efendi (2022), who investigated the

incorporation of character education into academic courses and demonstrated its integration with conventional disciplines.

Similarly, Table 11 presents the Significant Relationship Between the demographic profile of the respondents and the extent of implementation of the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education in terms of the Extracurricular Program.

Educational background (p-value = 0.005) and proficiency level of teachers (p-value = 0.001) impact the extent of implementation of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approaches to Character Education in Extracurricular Programs. Conversely, the number of classes handled showed no significant relationship with the extent of implementation of the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Extracurricular Programs (p-value = 0.227).

Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the extent of implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education in terms of extracurricular programs is rejected.

The demographic profile of teachers, as supported by Febriantina et al. (2021), can serve as the cornerstone for developing individuals with moral leadership qualities, integrity, and an understanding of the value of tolerance and cooperation in a multicultural community when character education is implemented effectively.

Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Respondents and Level of Effectiveness of Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to Learners' Development

Tables 12, 13, 14, and 15 presented the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education for learners' development.

Table 12 presents the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education in terms of learners' development and behavioral change.

The Proficiency level (p-value = 0.000) and educational background (p-value = 0.000) significantly impact the effectiveness of character education on learners' development in terms of Behavioral Change. Conversely, the number of classes handled showed no significant relationship (p-value = 0.182).

Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the level of effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education for learners' development in terms of behavioral change is rejected. This aligns with Skellie's (2024) contextual

analysis, which posits that learners' behavior is the most significant variable in determining students' academic achievement in Character Education.

Table 13 presents the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education to learners' development in terms of Social-Emotional Skills.

The Proficiency level (p -value = 0.000) and the number of classes handled (p -value = 0.046) significantly impact the effectiveness of character education. However, educational background showed no significant relationship (p -value = 0.403). Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the level of effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education for learners' development in terms of social-emotional skills is rejected.

This supports the Szabo et. al. (2020) study, which compared social-emotional learning (SEL) with character education scores from recent public examinations. They found that students with higher Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) levels consistently outperformed their peers with lower SEL levels in character education. This positive correlation may be due to the earlier emphasis on behavior and discipline in schools attended by students with higher Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) scores. The study supported the claim that higher Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) resulted from the character education of learners and its integration into the curriculum.

Table 14 presents the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education for learners' development in terms of Ethical Decision-Making.

Teacher's Proficiency level (p -value = 0.015) significantly impacts the effectiveness of character education. Conversely, educational background (p -value = 0.085) and number of classes handled (P -value = 0.166) showed no significant relationships. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the level of effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education in learners' development in terms of ethical decision-making is rejected. This finding aligns with that of Koçak et al. (2021), who found that family ethical decision-making was a particularly important factor in preparing their young children for school.

Lastly, Table 15 presents the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education to learners' development in terms of Peer and Teacher Relationships.

Teachers' proficiency level (p -value = 0.003), educational background (p -value = 0.001), and the number of classes handled (p -value = 0.000) all significantly impact the

effectiveness of character education. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education for learners' development in terms of peer and teacher relationships is rejected.

This disagrees with Nugraha (2023), who suggests that character education in the 21st century can be achieved through the realization of democratic education by meeting the subsequent prerequisites, which do not include teachers' demographic profiles. Firstly, the practice of education should constantly prioritize justice and equality; Secondly, pupils' cultural competencies should be developed as a result of the learning process. These skills include self-awareness, respect, and an understanding of different cultures, as well as the ability to work effectively with a range of cultural variations.

Significant Relationship Between the Extent of implementation of a Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education and the Level of Effectiveness of the Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive Approach in Character Education to learners' development

As shown in Tables 16 and 17, there is a significant relationship between the extent of implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education and its effectiveness in learners' development.

Table 16 illustrates the significant relationship between the extent of implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education, as outlined in the Academic Curriculum, and its effectiveness in learners' development.

The results indicate a strong positive correlation between the extent of implementation in terms of Academic Curriculum and level of effectiveness across Behavioral Change (r-value =0.78), Social Emotional Skills (r-value =0.71), Ethical Decision Making (r-value =0.72), and Peer Teacher Relationship (r-value =0.68), with all relationships being statistically significant.

This agrees with Battle and Lewis (2022), who highlighted a statistically significant relationship between family character education and academic success. This means that students whose families actively engage in character education programs tend to achieve higher academic performance. The study suggests that when families participate, it has a positive influence on their children's learning experiences.

Table 17 illustrates the significant relationship between the extent of implementing a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education, as reflected in the Extracurricular program, and its effectiveness in learners' development.

Furthermore, the results also indicate a strong positive correlation between the extent of implementation in terms of Extracurricular Program and level of effectiveness across Behavioral Change (r-value =0.83), Social Emotional Skills (r-value =0.69), Ethical

Decision Making (r-value =0.86), and Peer Teacher Relationship (r-value =0.73), with all relationships being statistically significant.

Therefore, the null hypothesis, which indicates that the extent of implementation of character education has no significant influence on its effectiveness in learners' development, is rejected.

This finding indicates that the more comprehensive and deliberate the implementation of character education, the more successful it is in fostering positive development in students. Olsen (2020) supports this claim by demonstrating, through a school-wide program, that teachers perceived noticeable improvements in student behavior across several key character traits, including respect, courtesy, self-respect, and responsibility. This suggests that when character education is systematically and intentionally applied, it can significantly enhance students' attitudes and behaviors, underscoring the importance of a well-structured and proactive approach to character development in educational settings.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. In terms of the demographic profile of teacher respondents, most teachers are classified as Proficient or Highly Proficient. Most teachers hold a Bachelor's Degree, followed by a Master's Degree and a Doctoral Degree. On average, most teachers handle 4 to 6 classes at a time.
2. The implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education in terms of the Academic Curriculum and extracurricular program is Fully Implemented.
3. The implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to character education is Very Effective in learners' development in terms of behavioral change, social-emotional skills, ethical decision-making, and peer and teacher relationships.
4. There is a significant relationship between the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of teachers' proficiency level, educational attainment, and the extent of implementation of a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach in character education in terms of academic curriculum and extra-curricular programs.
5. There is a significant relationship between the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of teachers' proficiency level, educational attainment, and number of classes handled, and the effectiveness of character education in learners' development

in terms of behavioral change, social-emotional skills, ethical decision-making, and peer-teacher relationships.

6. There is a significant relationship between the extent of implementation of character education in terms of academic curriculum and extra-curricular programs and the effectiveness in learners' development in behavioral change, social-emotional skills, ethical decision-making, and peer and teacher relationships.

Recommendations

Considering the conclusions and the significance of the study, the following recommendation is proposed:

1. First, the Department of Education may use the findings to refine policies and guidelines for character education and emphasize a comprehensive, intentional, and proactive approach to ensure that character education is fully integrated into academic curricula and extra-curricular programs.

2. It is also recommended that curriculum designers integrate best practices from the study into character education curriculum frameworks and ensure that these frameworks are comprehensive and intentionally designed to address behavioral change, social-emotional skills, ethical decision-making, and peer relationships.

3. Moreover, it is recommended that school administration utilize the study's findings to inform strategic planning and resource allocation for character education initiatives by focusing on interventions that align with the comprehensive approach.

4. As such, it is also recommended that schools provide additional support or training for teachers in the implementation of character education in academic and extra-curricular programs to create nurturing classroom environments that support character development.

5. Furthermore, it is also recommended that implemented character education programs prioritize student development, emphasizing virtues, ethical decision-making, and interpersonal skills, and continuously gather feedback from students to refine and improve these programs.

6. Continuous evaluation should be established to assess the extent of implementation and effectiveness of character education programs to make necessary adjustments and improvements to the academic curriculum and extracurricular activities.

7. Lastly, the variables not covered by this study can serve as avenues for further research by exploring the impact of a Comprehensive, Intentional, and Proactive

Approach to character education in various educational settings and contexts, thereby building a broader understanding of its effectiveness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research was conducted in full compliance with ethical guidelines to ensure the dignity, rights, and welfare of all participants. Before participation, all individuals were fully informed of the nature, purpose, and potential risks and benefits of the study. Informed consent was obtained from each participant, ensuring that participation was voluntary and not coerced. Participants were assured of anonymity and confidentiality, with all personal data stored securely and accessed only by authorized researchers. Ethical approval for this study was granted by the Schools Division Superintendent, ensuring that the research complies with institutional and international ethical standards, including respect for privacy, the right to withdraw at any time, and the minimization of potential harm. No vulnerable populations were involved without appropriate safeguards, and the research findings will be shared responsibly, ensuring that they do not misrepresent data or lead to any adverse consequences for participants.

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